

Characterization of Microdroplets through Image Processing: A Reinterpretation in Java

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RESUME

Computer Graphics and Image Processing are two areas that have stood out in the current scenario due to the considerable growth in technological applications, which has allowed the resolution of increasingly complex problems. In a simplified view, computer graphics (CG) seeks photorealistic images of computer-generated three-dimensional scenes, while digital image processing (PDI) attempts to reconstruct a three-dimensional scene from a real image obtained through a camera. In this sense, PDI seeks an opposite procedure to CG, analysis instead of synthesis, but both areas act on the same knowledge, which includes, among other aspects, the interaction between lighting and objects and projections of a three-dimensional scene in an image plane. The article aims to re-read a program developed for the treatment of digital images acquired using the Direct Laminar Incidence (DLI) technique developed for the quantification and characterization of microdroplets arising from nebulizer mist, for this purpose the program will be transcribed for the JAVA language, as it is a more widespread and easier to understand computational language today (DOUGLAS A. LYON, 1999). It is expected that the new program can be used on other platforms, which previously would not have been possible due to it being in MATLAB.

Key Words: Microdroplets, Java, Direct Laminar Incidence.

INTRODUCTION

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Digital image processing generates images that can be acquired using video cameras, flatbed scanners, tomographs, satellites, etc. These images can be stored on a hard disk or other storage devices, such as magnetic tapes and optical disks. The stored image will be processed to meet the most varied objectives: compression, enhancement, pattern recognition, etc. The acquired or subsequently processed image can be viewed on various display devices: photographic film, printer, computer screen, etc. And they can also be transmitted to other locations through communication systems.

We can understand an image as a compact way of representing a lot of information. In an image processing system, this information can go through different forms of representation. Therefore, the image processing steps describe the flow of this information as objective data defined by the application (CASTLEMAN, 1996; ZHOU,2010a; ZHOU,2010b).

IMAGE PROCESSING

Segmentation consists of subdividing an image into its constituent parts or objects, where an object in this context refers to a convex component. After segmentation, each object is described with respect to its geometric and topological properties. Based on this description, the recognition of each object results in a labelled image, where pixels that belong to different objects have different labels associated with them (HARALICK,1973; HE, 2016). The semantic interpretation of a set of labelled objects in the domain of an application completes the analysis process, giving rise to an action (GONZALEZ, 2008; GONZALEZ, 2009; RUSS, 2019). For example, a system can recognize digits in a barcode image and interpret them as the access number for a given product in a supermarket. The action in this case may be to record the value of the product upon purchase. Segmentation is one of the main and most studied operations in image processing. Thus, segmentation can also be modelled as a combinatorial optimization problem, in which an optimal region is sought according to some similarity criterion between elements in the same region (JAIN,1991).

Image segmentation is a fundamental step in image processing systems. It is a process of direct dependence on the scene to be analysed, where geometric aspects,

configuration, and type of sensor are used to digitize the image (ZHOU, 2010b; MALLAT, 1989).

Figure 1 - Typical flow in image analysis
Source: Adapted from ZHOU, 2010b.

Image segmentation plays a crucial role in automatic visual systems, because the perception of objects of interest in a scene is a preliminary step for image recognition and interpretation, therefore, segmentation plays a fundamental role in enabling the study of the droplets recorded in the images.

METHODOLOGY

The development of the direct laminar incidence (ILD) technique, this technique consists of focusing the mist from the nebulizer on a blade and capturing the image using an ultrafast camera to acquire micro drops. This process highlighted the need to use digital image processing as a tool for characterizing the size of these microdroplets, as well as the possibility of counting and classifying them by bands. The program chosen at this time was MATLAB, as it was a program available at the time and in the public domain. But today requires programs that adapt to the various technological platforms that exist today – such as the use of mobile phones and smartphones. There is a need to update the program to meet these new guidelines, so a transcription of the MATLAB digital image processing program was implemented into a digital image program in JAVA. The initial source code was rewritten and adapted to the new language.

The transcript of the new program is described in the link below, easily accessible to the public. <https://github.com/danilobarretoooo/image-processing-techniques>

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This access link contains all the code that was transcribed into the JAVA program and its interfaces to create the processed images of the mist microdroplets from the nebulizer using the DLI technique.

RESULTS

The image processing used in this study seeks to quantify the droplets present in the images captured during the experiments aimed at characterizing their respective diameters.

The first step in processing consists of segmenting the images. The objective is to try to differentiate in the image all the regions that represent the droplets from the rest of the image.

This segmentation is done using the JAVA program by comparing the image to be processed with a reference image (image of the same region filmed during the experiment, but without the presence of droplets). An example of a real image (a) alongside a reference image (b) can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2 - (a) Image to be processed (b) Reference image.

Source: Own authorship.

Figure 3 presents an example of an original image together with the image obtained after applying the described program.

Figure 3 - (a) Original image (b) Image obtained after applying the segmentation technique used. Source: Own authorship

At this point in the processing there is the distribution of all diameters of the droplets identified in the image. What is done next is to create histograms to represent the distribution of diameters found in the image in the desired way.

CONCLUSION

In this article, we explore reimagining the digital imaging program from MatLab to the digital imaging program in Java. Throughout the subsequent sections, we examine the crucial role of image pre-processing in improving the quality of visual data, the importance of segmentation in identifying significant regions, and feature extraction as a key step in effectively representing the information contained in images. The diverse practical applications of image processing, from medicine to computer vision in autonomous vehicles, are important to recognize current challenges, such as robustness to lighting variations and the interpretation of characteristics in complex environments. The field of image processing continues to evolve, driven by advances in machine learning, computer vision, and specialized hardware. The increasing use of data-driven approaches and the development of more interpretable techniques promise to further transform reality. In short, image processing is a constantly expanding interdisciplinary area, with significant applications in several areas.

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FUTURE WORKS

Technological advancement encourages researchers and professionals to explore new frontiers in digital image processing. An in-depth understanding of the challenges, interdisciplinary collaboration and the continuous search for innovative solutions are fundamental to the progress and practical application of this tool that is constantly evolving today. The feasibility of using the digital image processing program in JAVA recapitulates key findings in addressing current challenges and launches a call to action for future research in the fascinating field of image processing.

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